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Almond, its Bioecological Characteristics and Agrotechnical Features

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***Abstract:** In Uzbekistan, almond plantations are located in the Fergana Valley, in the Bostanlyk district of the Tashkent region, in the vicinity of the Kattakurgan reservoir, in the Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Jizzakh and Syrdarya regions. Among the existing local varieties, high-yielding late-flowering forms are of economic importance.*

***Key words:** grooved, smooth or rough, color.*

Introduction

Common almond belongs to the Rosaceae family and, along with other species, is widespread in Asia Minor and Central Asia, Transcaucasia, Afghanistan, China. In its cultivated form, this plant is found in the countries of Central Asia, the Mediterranean, Iran, Iraq, Afghanistan, Pakistan, the USA, Argentina, Chile, Australia, and South Africa (Richter, 1958, 1985; Yadrov, 1981; Yaskina, 1980).

In Central Asia, it is found in western Kapetdag (Ayder), in western Tien Shan - on the slopes of the Fergana Range, in the Fergana and Kurama Ranges, in the vicinity of Issyk-Kul, in part of the river basin or, in Pamir-Alai, Gissar, Turkestan, Zeravshan, in the Babatag Mountains (Pokhomova, 1961; Kalmokov, 1973).

Cultivated almond forests are developed on the island of Java, in Australia, and South Africa. In its highly cultivated form, it is grown in Italy, the US state of California, Spain, Northern Iran, Turkey and a number of other countries. In Uzbekistan, almond plantations are located in the Fergana Valley, in the Bostanlyk district of the Tashkent region, in the vicinity of the Kattakurgan reservoir, in the Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Jizzakh and Syrdarya regions. Among the existing local varieties, high-yielding late-flowering forms are of economic importance.

Well-developed trees reach 4-6 m, in some cases - up to 10 m. Mature almond trees can withstand winter frosts down to -27 ° C. The crown is wide, rounded, broom-shaped, sometimes cylindrical. The trunk reaches 20-35 cm in diameter, the branches are straight or curved, without thorns, with numerous small shoots. The flowers are large, 3-4 cm in diameter, usually solitary, the peduncle is naked, 3-5

mm long. Almonds require exposure to temperatures of 0–6°C for 100 hours in winter, after which only positive temperatures are required. For leaves to appear, the sum of positive temperatures must be 1100°C, but this figure varies depending on the variety. In this regard, varieties are divided into early-flowering, mid-flowering and late-flowering.

Methodology

The fruit is a hard drupe 1.0–6.0 cm long, attached to the peduncle, covered with a dense peel of a light green color. As it ripens, the peel cracks, usually along a longitudinal groove. The nut is found in shapes from round to cylindrical. The shell can be dotted-porous or grooved, smooth or rough, the color varies from light yellow to dark brown. The shell hardness varies from soft (easily broken) to very hard (stony).

The weight of an almond kernel is 0.71–5.67 g, in wild forms – 0.61–4.03 g. Common almonds have the property of cross-pollination. Pollination is carried out mainly by wind, partly by bees. The almond tree lives 60–100 years. The first fruits appear in the 2–3rd year. In mountainous conditions, the fruits ripen in the second half of August, in foothill areas – in August–September. The average yield is 10–15 kg of peeled almonds from one tree. High-yielding varieties can produce 3.2–21.4 kg per tree. On irrigated lands (at an altitude of 900 m above sea level), the yield of common almond varieties is 2–5 kg, on terraced slopes (1100–1300 m) six-year-old trees yield 8–10 kg from each tree. Almonds 6–8 years old, growing on dry lands, depending on the variety, yield 0.7–3.8 kg of peeled nuts. Common almonds are drought-resistant and heat-loving, along with pistachios, they are among the most drought-resistant trees. In large trees growing on rocky soils, the root system extends to a depth of up to 6 m and a radius of up to 7 m. Common almonds are of great economic importance, their fruits are a valuable food product. Due to the high quality of taste, it is used in the confectionery industry, as well as in the perfume and pharmaceutical industries. Depending on the growing conditions and variety, the content of fat, sugar, protein and ash, as well as the weight of the almond kernel, varies.

Results and discussion

In the Bostanlyk district, the yield of kernels from the highest quality varieties is 37.7–53.3%. In the foothill regions, the yield of kernels from the nut is 28.9–64.7%, and for the best Crimean varieties – 38.5–63%.

Chemical composition of almond kernels:

- fat – 35–67%,
- sugar – 2–10%,
- protein – 16.5–34.0%,
- ash – 2.9–5%,
- fiber – 2.46–3.48%,
- lignin – 2.45–4.39%.

The Zavetny variety was bred in the branch of the R.R. Schroeder Research Institute of Horticulture and Viticulture. Resistant to spring frosts. Bears fruit annually. Moderately resistant to diseases. The best pollinators are the Tungich and Kolkhozny varieties. Begins bearing fruit in the 4th year after planting. It has a high yield: 12–15 kg per tree on irrigated lands, 4–5 kg on dry lands. Nut weight is 2.16 g, the shell is standard, the kernel yield is 66.7%, the fat content is 52.9%. The Tyan Shansky variety was bred in the same branch. Despite its early flowering, it is resistant to spring frosts. It is

slightly affected by diseases. Fruit ripening is average. Begins bearing fruit in the 4th year. It has a high yield: up to 10 kg per tree on irrigated lands, up to 3.5 kg on dry lands. The nut is large, weighs 2.9 g, has a thin shell, kernel yield is 49.2%, fat content is 56.1%. In dry land conditions, the quality of the nuts decreases by 20-22%. Ugam - this almond variety was selected by the branch among seedlings of the Western European variety "Princess". Drought-resistant, blooms late. Resistant to spring frosts. Bears fruit annually. Moderately resistant to clasterosporium, slightly affected by "sheep" disease. Begins to bear fruit in the 4th year after planting. The best pollinators are the varieties "Kylychsimon" and "Nikitsky-62". Blooms April 5-8, ripens August 17-30. The nut is large (37×23×16 mm), pointed, rounded at the base. The yield on irrigated lands is up to 17 kg per tree, on dry lands - up to 3 kg. The weight of the nut is 2.7 g, the shell is of standard hardness, the kernel yield is 42.8%. Fat content is 63%, sugar - 6%. On dry lands, the weight of the nut decreases by 12-13%. Tungich - The variety was bred in Uzbekistan. The tree is medium-sized. It blooms in the first ten days of April. It is slightly affected by diseases. Drought-resistant. The nut is medium-sized, high quality, weight is 1.96 g, the shell is light, the kernel yield is 46.7%, fat content is 60%. Ripens in early September. The yield is 8-11 c/ha. It begins to bear fruit in the 4th year. Zoned in Uzbekistan.

Yaltinsky - Bred in Crimea. Medium-sized tree. Blossoms late, resistant to spring frosts. Bears fruit annually. Large nut, weight - 3.26 g, soft shell, kernel yield - 40.3%, fat content - 54%. Productivity - 7.6 c/ha. Begins bearing fruit in the 3rd year. Zoned in all the republics of Central Asia.

Nikitsky late-flowering. Bred in Crimea. Characterized by late flowering and resistance to spring frosts. Large nut, weight - 3.07 g, soft shell, kernel yield - 47.8%, fat content - 53%. High-yielding variety - up to 20 c/ha. Begins bearing fruit in the 4th year. Zoned in Tajikistan. The following varieties are economically valuable for cultivation in the Central Asian republics: "Bostanlyk late-flowering", "Dessert", "Kolkhozny", "Nikitsky-6", "Nikitsky late-flowering", "Kylychsimon" and "Turkmen excellent". The varieties "Languedoc" and others are also recommended.

In the foothill dryland areas, precipitation is uneven. Summer is dry, there is practically no precipitation. In winter, cold weather and maximum precipitation prevail, spring is wet and warm, and then hot and dry summer quickly sets in without rain. Dryland areas are undulating foothill hills, alternating with low elongated smooth hills and foothill plains, forming characteristic landscapes. They have similar thermal and humidity conditions. The soils are brown earth, contain 0.32–0.72% humus, a weakly expressed humus horizon and small reserves of nitrogen (0.039%) and phosphorus (0.15%). Groundwater lies at a depth of about 10 m and is highly mineralized. The climate of the region is sharply continental, characterized by sharp daily and seasonal temperature fluctuations. The average monthly air temperature in summer is 29.8 °C, the maximum temperature is observed in July and reaches 38.1 °C. From August, the temperature gradually decreases, and its minimum values occur in January (1.75 °C), and in February it can reach -9.9 °C. Annual precipitation varies from 183.5 mm to 353.9 mm. In rainfed areas, the depth of moisture penetration into the soil directly depends on the amount of precipitation. In different years, soil moisture reaches a depth of 0.8 m to 1.5–2 m.

In uncultivated rainfed lands, the amount of moisture in the 20–200 cm horizon gradually decreases during the growing season due to evaporation through soil capillaries and its consumption by annual grasses. Soil cultivation on hilly rainfed lands with medium moisture content is carried out taking into account that these lands have not been previously cultivated and were fallow. Since the relief allows for continuous cultivation, fallow lands are initially plowed to a depth of 40–45 cm with a plantation plow. Further soil cultivation is carried out using the black fallow system, aimed at preserving soil

moisture and controlling weeds. Deep plowing is carried out in the fall of the first year using a PN-4-35 or PLN-4-35 mounted plow in combination with T-44 or DT-75 tractors.

In the spring and summer of the following year, the soil is cultivated 2-4 times. For this, KPN-4 cultivators are used in combination with a DT-75 tractor.

- The first cultivation is carried out in the second ten-day period of April to a depth of 8-10 cm, when the main amount of precipitation has already fallen and weeds are actively developing.
- The second cultivation is carried out in the first or second ten-day period of May to a depth of 10-12 cm.
- The third cultivation is carried out in the first ten-day period of June to a depth of up to 15 cm.

Each cultivation saturates the soil with oxygen, destroys capillary channels, reduces moisture loss and destroys weeds. As a result, microbiological and aerobic processes improve, and the soil retains moisture and heat better. In the fall or early winter, repeated plowing is carried out to a depth of 25-30 cm to accumulate winter-spring precipitation. Timing and methods of planting seedlings - In moderately provided hilly rainfed lands, the optimal time for planting common almonds is considered to be warm days of January and early spring. The distribution of precipitation in the region is clearly expressed and is divided into two periods:

- "Dry" (June - October) - the amount of precipitation does not exceed 1-3 mm, but in some years up to 60 mm of precipitation falls in October, while November can be dry.
- "Relatively wet" (November - May) - minimal precipitation is observed at the beginning of November and December, as well as in May. The main rains begin in the second ten days of December and are accompanied by a decrease in temperature.

Delay in planting seedlings in moderately provided rainfed areas until the second half of March - April sharply reduces their survival rate. When planting high-quality almond varieties, it is possible to use the LPA-1 machine. During autumn planting, after marking the planting sites, the holes can be dug mechanically using the KPYa-100 deep digger to a depth of 50 cm. When planting, it is taken into account that the budding site should be 5-7 cm below the soil level. Before planting, damaged and broken parts of the root system are cut off and treated with an aqueous solution of humus. After planting, the soil around the seedling is compacted to eliminate voids in the soil, which helps to increase its survival rate.

Plant placement scheme - In conditions of moderately provided upland-lowland rainfed lands, the placement scheme is the main factor influencing the growth and fruiting of common almonds, since they are photophilous and have a root system that seeks to make maximum use of the moisture accumulated in the soil. If agrotechnical requirements are met, common almonds, like other fruit trees, grow well and produce high yields. The first cultivation is carried out in the second or third ten-day period of April to destroy the capillary channels in the soil formed over the winter and to destroy weeds. The second cultivation is carried out in the second ten-day period of May, when the region receives the main amount of precipitation. Its purpose is to destroy the surface crust of the soil and remove weeds. The third cultivation is carried out in the first or second ten-day period of June and is aimed at destroying newly sprouted weeds. To fully cover the entire area of plant nutrition, cultivations are carried out perpendicular to each other. On low-moisture dryland, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and organic fertilizers are applied from the second year after planting and then every 2-3 years. Nitrogen fertilizers are used in the form of ammonium nitrate or ammonium sulfate,

phosphorus fertilizers - in the form of simple or double superphosphate, potassium fertilizers - in the form of potassium salt. Fertilizer rates:

- nitrogen — 100-120 kg/ha,
- phosphorus — 70-90 kg/ha,
- Potassium — 40-40 kg/ha.

Conclusion

In dryland conditions, the application of mineral fertilizers primarily depends on the soil moisture level. Low-soluble and poorly accessible potassium and phosphorus fertilizers, as well as nitrogen fertilizers, are applied to the soil only in the fall. Fertilizers are evenly distributed between the rows and then incorporated into the soil during autumn plowing. Therefore, before the start of autumn plowing, fertilizers must already be applied. Fertilizers are applied using PRVM-3 and PRVM-1400 units in combination with a DT-75 tractor. Organic fertilizers are applied starting from the third year of plant life, then every 2-3 years. The manure application rate is 6 t/ha. The spreader ROS-3 is used for application in combination with the tractor T-40A.

Protection against pests and diseases - In the agricultural technology of industrial cultivation of common almonds, the control of pests and diseases is of great importance. On dry lands, almond plantations are affected by pests such as aphids, spider mites, weevils, as well as diseases such as leaf spot and burn. To combat pests in early spring, before the buds begin to open, trees are sprayed with a 40% solution of DNOC (10-20 kg/ha). If the treatment was not carried out in early spring, then during the period of bud awakening against weevils, a 40% emulsion concentrate of phosphamide (0.8-4 kg/ha), Antio (40% e.c., 1.2-4 kg/ha), Karbofos (40% e.c., 1-3 kg/ha), Trichlormetaphos (50% e.c., 1.2-4 kg/ha) are used.

To protect against fruit aphids after flowering, use a 40% solution of DNOC (10-20 kg/ha) or emulsion preparations No. 30, 20A, 30C, 30CC, 30M. To combat leaf spotting and burns, infected trees are sprayed with a 3-4% solution of Bordeaux mixture at a rate of 1000 l/ha. Treatment of plantings with chemicals is carried out at intervals of 2-5 years using the ON-400-5 sprayer in combination with MTZ-80 or T-28-4 tractors.

Suggested literature

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